

Non-invasive Methods For Accelerating Orthodontic Tooth Movement: A Review

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Abstract

Reducing the duration of orthodontic treatment has become an important goal in contemporary practice, driven by patient expectations and the need to minimize treatment related complications. This review outlines the biological mechanisms underlying orthodontic tooth movement (OTM) and discusses non-invasive approaches developed to enhance its rate. Tooth movement occurs through a coordinated response of the periodontal ligament and alveolar bone, where controlled mechanical forces stimulate bone resorption by osteoclasts and bone formation by osteoblasts. Several biochemical mediators, such as prostaglandins, vitamin D3, parathyroid hormone, cytokines, osteocalcin, and platelet-rich plasma, have been investigated for their ability to influence these cellular processes and accelerate tooth movement. Additional agents, including relaxin, thyroid hormones, nicotine, and substance P, may alter tissue response, although their clinical use is limited by safety concerns and variable outcomes. Advances in gene-based strategies, particularly those targeting the RANK/RANKL/OPG pathway, offer new possibilities for precise control of bone remodeling. Despite promising findings, further clinical research is essential to confirm their safety, effectiveness, and applicability in routine orthodontic care.

Keywords: Orthodontic tooth movement, accelerated orthodontics, bone remodeling, non-invasive techniques, RANK/RANKL/OPG system.

Introduction

Orthodontics has evolved over time to address the needs of both clinicians and patients. Advances in arch wire materials and bracket designs have improved the efficiency of treatment. Today, an increasing number of both adolescents and adults are seeking orthodontic care. A major concern for many patients is the length of treatment, which typically ranges from two to three years with fixed appliances. Extended treatment duration can increase the risk of complications such as dental caries, external root resorption, gingival recession, and reduced patient compliance.¹ Fortunately, the field of orthodontics is experiencing a significant shift with the introduction of accelerated orthodontic techniques. This modern method combines multiple strategies to accelerate tooth movement, allowing patients to reach their desired outcomes in a significantly reduced timeframe.

Accelerated orthodontics refers to a group of techniques designed to increase the rate of orthodontic tooth movement and reduce overall treatment time while maintaining treatment efficiency and stability.

Various strategies have been explored in both laboratory and clinical settings to shorten treatment time; however, many of these methods still involve uncertainties and unresolved questions.

Orthodontic tooth movement is initiated by mechanical forces and progresses through coordinated remodeling of the alveolar bone and the periodontal ligament (PDL).² The rate and direction of orthodontic tooth movement are influenced by the magnitude of the applied force and the biological response of the periodontal ligament (PDL).³

Application of orthodontic force alters local blood flow, leading to changes in the periodontal ligament (PDL) environment. This process triggers the release of inflammatory mediators such as cytokines, metabolites of arachidonic acid, colony stimulating factors (CSFs), growth factors, and neurotransmitters, which collectively promote bone remodeling. The aim of this article is to examine different non-invasive methods used to accelerate

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orthodontic tooth movement and assess their relevance in clinical practice.

Mechanism of Orthodontic Tooth Movement

Orthodontic tooth movement occurs through the biological response of the periodontal ligament (PDL) and alveolar bone when subjected to mechanical forces.⁴ Alveolar bone undergoes continuous modeling and remodeling, with new bone forming on the tension side and bone resorption occurring on the side under compression.⁵ This process occurs in three stages: an initial phase marked by rapid tooth displacement following force application, a lag phase with minimal or no movement, and a final phase characterized by a gradual or sometimes accelerated increase in movement. Cellular activity, along with cytokines and various signaling pathways, plays a key role in regulating these stages.^{6,7}

The rate of these processes depends on the activity of bone cells, including osteoclasts, osteoblasts, and osteocytes, which are regulated by both mechanical forces and biochemical signals. As a result, the rate and effectiveness of orthodontic tooth movement can be influenced by modifying the underlying biological mechanisms and pathways (Figure 1).^{8,9}

Figure 1: Basic principles and acceleration methods of orthodontic tooth movement (OTM)

Non-Invasive Methods for Accelerating Orthodontic Tooth Movement

Prostaglandins (Pgs)

Prostaglandins are chemical signaling molecules that belong to the eicosanoid family of hormones.¹⁰

Prostaglandins (PGs), especially PGE₂, function as powerful local lipid mediators involved in bone metabolism. They can stimulate osteoclast activity, making them useful for enhancing orthodontic tooth movement. Early studies by Yamasaki and colleagues showed that local application of PGE₂ accelerated tooth movement in animal models, although higher doses were associated with increased root resorption. The addition of calcium helped reduce this adverse effect while preserving the acceleration benefits. When PGE₂ was used along with calcium gluconate, the calcium ions helped reduce root resorption while still enhancing the rate of orthodontic tooth movement.¹¹

Yamasaki and colleagues investigated the influence of prostaglandins on orthodontic tooth movement in *Macaca fuscata* monkeys and evaluated potential effects on gingival tissues. Their findings showed that local injection of PGE₁ or PGE₂ in the gingiva distal to the canine significantly increased the rate of tooth movement, approximately doubling it compared to the untreated control side. No harmful effects on the gingiva were observed, except for mild discomfort associated with tooth movement. Despite these promising results, concerns about possible systemic effects, such as impacts on kidney function and bone health, remain. Ongoing research is focused on safer delivery methods, including controlled release systems and calcium combinations, to improve safety while maintaining effectiveness.^{12,13,14}

Vitamin D3

1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol (1,25[OH]₂D₃), also known as calcitriol, is the biologically active form of vitamin D and plays a key role in maintaining calcium balance. It helps regulate serum calcium and phosphate levels by enhancing their absorption in the intestines and reabsorption in the kidneys. In addition, calcitriol supports bone mineralization and suppresses parathyroid hormone (PTH) secretion. At the microscopic level, a higher number of mononuclear osteoclasts were recruited and activated, leading to increased alveolar bone resorption on the pressure side. No significant clinical, histological, or biochemical adverse effects were observed.¹⁵

Intraligamentous injection of 1,25D in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) in cats at weekly interval demonstrated 60% further tooth movement than matched control teeth.¹⁶

Kale et al. conducted a comparative study on the effects of vitamin D₃ and prostaglandins on orthodontic tooth movement. Both agents were found to significantly enhance tooth movement compared to the control group. The vitamin D₃ group showed a greater number of osteoblasts on the outer surface of the alveolar bone than the prostaglandin group. The authors concluded that 1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol promotes tooth movement by facilitating bone remodeling and also supports the regeneration of periodontal tissues, which may contribute to better post-treatment stability.^{17,18} Due to widespread vitamin D deficiency, using vitamin D metabolites may accelerate orthodontic tooth movement, but further studies are needed for safety assessment.

Relaxin

Relaxin promotes bone cell activity and increases connective tissue turnover. It is primarily associated with remodeling of soft tissues rather than direct effects on bone.¹⁹ Madan, Lui, and co-workers assessed the effects of relaxin on orthodontic tooth movement and the periodontal ligament (PDL) in rat models. They observed increased collagen formation on the tension side and reduced collagen on the pressure side. The study concluded that human relaxin did not significantly accelerate tooth movement in rats; instead, it mainly decreased PDL organization and mechanical strength, leading to increased tooth mobility during the early phase of orthodontic treatment.^{20,21}

Concerns have been raised about the possible limitations of relaxin use in orthodontics. It may weaken periodontal ligament structure by reducing its organization and mechanical strength, leading to increased tooth mobility. These effects also raise doubts about long-term stability and the risk of relapse after treatment. The exact mechanism of relaxin in tooth movement is still unclear, highlighting the need for further well designed clinical studies to evaluate its safety and effectiveness.^{22,23}

Parathyroid Hormone (PTH)

Parathyroid hormone (PTH) is produced by the parathyroid glands and plays a key role in regulating calcium levels in the body. It increases serum calcium by enhancing intestinal absorption, reducing renal excretion, and mobilizing calcium from bone. In orthodontics, PTH influences tooth movement by binding to PTH-1 receptors on osteoblasts, which stimulates insulin like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) production. This enhances osteoblast formation, improves cell survival, increases RANKL expression, and activates osteoclasts. Its effect on tooth movement depends on dosage and exposure pattern: continuous elevation promotes bone resorption, whereas intermittent release can have an anabolic effect on bone.^{19,24}

Li et al. studied PTH effects on tooth movement in rats and found that intermittent administration promotes bone formation, while prolonged continuous exposure increases bone resorption. Intermittent dosing enhances both osteoblast and osteoclast activity, thereby accelerating bone remodeling and turnover.²⁵

Soma's rat study showed that continuous subcutaneous infusion of PTH (10 µg/100 g body weight/day) increased mesial movement of the maxillary first molar. Tooth movement was accelerated 2–3 times due to a rise in osteoclast numbers and enhanced bone resorption confined mainly to the pressure side, without affecting other alveolar regions. PTH also promoted rapid clearance of necrotic tissue by stimulating proteolytic enzyme release, potentially reducing root resorption. However, systemic use may affect weight bearing bones, so local application is considered more suitable in orthodontic treatment.²⁶

Cytokines

Cytokines and inflammatory mediators, such as prostaglandin E₂, are believed to stimulate bone remodeling. They may do so by attracting osteoclast precursor cells from circulation and promoting their differentiation and activation, thereby enhancing bone resorption.

Teixeira et al. evaluated cytokine expression in the periodontal ligament during orthodontic tooth movement using a rat model. The animals were divided into four groups: force only, force with flap surgery, force with flap and bone perforations, and a control group. Analysis showed increased expression of multiple cytokines after force application, with the highest levels observed in the group receiving combined force, flap, and perforations, indicating enhanced inflammatory and remodeling activity.²⁷

Osteocalcin

Osteocalcin (OC) is the most abundant non-collagenous protein in bone matrix. It binds strongly to calcium and hydroxyapatite and is considered to regulate mineralization and bone formation. Additionally, osteocalcin may act as a chemoattractant, promoting the recruitment of osteoclast precursors and mature osteoclasts.

Hashimoto et al. studied the effect of osteocalcin on orthodontic tooth movement in rats by administering different doses locally near the maxillary first molar. Compared to controls, the group receiving 1 µg osteocalcin showed a significant increase in tooth movement, with approximately 152% greater displacement, indicating its potential role in enhancing bone remodeling and accelerating tooth movement.²⁸

Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP)

Platelet rich plasma (PRP) is an autologous concentration of platelets within a small volume of plasma. Platelet alpha granules contain growth factors and chemokines essential for healing and tissue repair. PRP has been widely studied in regenerative medicine, and recent research has explored its role in orthodontics.

Animal studies have shown that local PRP injections may enhance and accelerate orthodontic tooth movement.

Timamy et al. evaluated the effect of local PRP injections on orthodontic tooth movement in 15 female patients using a split-mouth design. Canine retraction was performed with stainless steel archwire and NiTi coil springs. The experimental side received PRP injections at specific intervals. Results showed a slightly higher rate of tooth movement on the PRP side compared to the control, indicating a modest acceleration effect.²⁹

Thyroid hormones

Thyroid hormones are commonly used to manage hypothyroidism and as replacement therapy after thyroidectomy. Administration of thyroxine enhances bone remodeling by increasing bone resorption and reducing bone density, possibly through stimulation of interleukin-1 (IL-1β) and osteoclast activity. In orthodontics, thyroid hormones can accelerate tooth movement in patients receiving this medication. Short-term, low dose use has also been associated with a reduced risk of force induced root resorption, likely due to modifications in bone remodeling and improved protection of dental tissues.³⁰

Shirazi et al. studied thyroxine effects on tooth movement in rats and found that a 20 µg/kg daily dose significantly increased orthodontic tooth movement.³¹

Nicotine

Nicotine, a toxic component of tobacco smoke, adversely affects overall health and bone biology. Studies show it impairs bone healing and regeneration, reduces implant integration, and contributes to alveolar bone loss and periodontal disease. In orthodontics, nicotine is associated with problems such as reduced bracket bonding, miniscrew failure, and disruption of normal bone remodeling processes. Manal et al. investigated the effect of nicotine on orthodontic tooth movement in rats by dividing them into different dosage groups. Nicotine was administered before and during force application. The highest dose group showed the greatest increase in tooth movement, while the control group had the least movement, indicating that nicotine accelerates orthodontic tooth movement in a dose dependent manner.³²

Substance P

Studies show that substance P levels increase in periodontal tissues during orthodontic tooth movement, suggesting its role in the inflammatory environment that influences tooth displacement. It acts as a chemoattractant for monocytes and lymphocytes and promotes immune cell activity. Research also indicates that substance P can function as a systemic injury signal, mobilizing mesenchymal stem cells into the bloodstream. These cells contribute to bone remodeling and immune regulation, thereby potentially affecting the rate of orthodontic tooth movement. An et al. studied the effect of substance P on orthodontic tooth movement in rats. Animals receiving substance P injections along with orthodontic force showed greater tooth movement compared to the control group. Measurements at days 7 and 14 indicated an approximately 1.3–1.5 times increase in movement, suggesting that substance P can enhance the rate of orthodontic tooth displacement.³³

Gene Therapy

Kanzaki et al. (2006) investigated local RANKL gene transfer to periodontal tissues using an HVJ envelope vector. The vector was applied near the palatogingival area of the maxillary first molar, and orthodontic force was delivered using a compressive spring. Tooth movement was measured with callipers. The RANKL-treated side showed greater movement (0.63 ± 0.06 mm) compared to the

control side (0.48 ± 0.05 mm), indicating enhanced orthodontic tooth movement.

Orthodontic tooth movement depends on bone remodeling. Studies show that on the pressure side, alveolar bone resorption occurs along with increased expression of RANKL during tooth movement. This activation promotes osteoclast formation and activity. Many pharmacological approaches aim to accelerate tooth movement by enhancing osteoclast mediated bone resorption through such pathways.

Orthodontic tooth movement relies on bone remodeling, where osteoclasts develop on the pressure side and resorb alveolar bone. Their formation is mainly controlled by RANKL and M-CSF, with RANKL produced by osteoblasts and stromal cells binding to RANK on osteoclast lineage cells. This activity is regulated by osteoprotegerin (OPG), which balances bone resorption. During orthodontic movement, increased RANKL expression has been observed, confirming its role in site-specific remodeling. (Figure 2)³⁴

Figure 2: RANK/RANKL/OPG system in bone remodeling

Kanzaki et al. (2006) investigated local RANKL gene transfer to periodontal tissues using an HVJ envelope vector. The vector was applied near the palatogingival area of the maxillary first molar, and orthodontic force was delivered using a compressive spring. Tooth movement was measured with callipers. The RANKL-treated side showed greater movement (0.63 ± 0.06 mm) compared to the control side (0.48 ± 0.05 mm), indicating enhanced orthodontic tooth movement.³⁵

Conclusion

Accelerated orthodontics represents a promising advancement aimed at reducing treatment duration while maintaining biological safety and treatment stability. Various non-invasive methods, including biochemical mediators such as prostaglandins, vitamin D, parathyroid hormone, cytokines, osteocalcin, and platelet-rich plasma, have demonstrated potential in enhancing orthodontic tooth movement through modulation of bone remodeling. Other agents like relaxin, thyroid hormones, nicotine, and substance P further influence periodontal and cellular responses. Gene therapy approaches targeting the RANK/RANKL/OPG pathway offer additional precision in regulating osteoclast activity. However, despite encouraging results, most techniques require further well controlled clinical studies to confirm long-term safety, predictability, and clinical applicability in routine orthodontic practice.

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